

Effect of curing conditions on physico-mechanical properties of metakaolin-based geopolymer concrete containing calcium carbide residue

Yawo Daniel Adufu¹ · Seick Omar Sore^{1,2} · Philbert Nshimiyimana¹ · Adamah Messan¹ · Gilles Escadeillas³

Abstract

Today, hydraulic concrete remains the most used construction material in spite of the very polluting character of its main binder, namely portland cement. However, alternatives exist, such as geopolymer concretes. Current studies reported that the performances of geopolymer concretes can significantly be affected by the curing conditions, among other parameters. The present study specifically assesses the physico-mechanical properties of geopolymer concrete produced in ambient conditions, i.e., cured at controlled temperature (20 ± 2 °C) and uncontrolled ambient temperatures (30 ± 5 °C) of the laboratory. The metakaolin (mk)-based geopolymer concrete was designed by partial substitution of mk with 10 to 15 wt% ccr (calcium carbide residue), a lime-rich industrial by-product. The concrete was characterized in fresh state and hardened state after curing for 7, 14, and 28 days. The results indicate that the curing temperature has a significant effect on the physico-mechanical properties of geopolymer concretes. Setting times are longer at 20 °C (> 2970 min) than at 30 °C (< 2500 min) for all mix designs. At 7 days, the compressive strength increased by 77% (6.1 to 10.8 mpa) and 67% (3.1 to 5.2 mpa), respectively, for the concrete containing 0 and 15% ccr cured from 20 to 30 °C. At 14 days, the compressive strength increased by 26% (12 to 15.2 mpa) for the concrete containing 15% ccr cured from 20 to 30 °C. Although their 7-day strengths are lower compared to the reference concrete, all the samples containing ccr reach better strength from the 14th day regardless of the curing temperature.

Introduction

The search for alternatives to conventional hydraulic concrete is increasingly attracting the attention of the scientific community due to the high-carbon footprint of Portland cement and the unavailability of its raw materials.

Alkali-activated aluminosilicates materials in general and their subclass geopolymers in particular have shown potential as alternative materials for not only their mechanical, sustainability, and durability performances compared to the hydraulic concrete, but also for the diversity of raw materials that can be used for their manufacture [1].

Among the factors which can hinder the geopolymerization reactions, the concentration of the activator, the stoichiometric proportions (molar ratios) of the aluminosilicates, the chemical composition of the precursor as well as the curing conditions constitute the most influential parameters. Previous studies have shown that the curing at about 60 °C for 24 h is necessary for a good geopolymerization [2]. Some researchers have proposed an approach for the design of geopolymers at ambient temperature, but it is clear that these so-called ambient conditions do not consider the climatic realities of some regions of the world. The studies conducted at ambient temperature are mostly done at around 20 °C [3]. In present study area, Burkina Faso, average monthly temperature is around 28 °C [4]. It would be counterproductive to define 20 °C as the ambient temperature in this case because

✉ Yawo Daniel Adufu
daniel.adufu@2ie-edu.org

¹ Laboratoire Eco-Matériaux et Habitats Durables (LEMHaD), Institut International d'Ingénierie de l'Eau et de l'Environnement (Institut 2iE), Rue de La Science, 01, BP 594, Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso

² Département Génie Civil de l'Institut Universitaire de Technologie/Laboratoire de Chimie et Energies Renouvelables (LaCER), Unité de Recherche en Physico Chimie et Technologie des Matériaux, Université Nazi Boni, B.P. 1091 Bobo 01, Bobo-Dioulasso, Burkina Faso

³ Laboratoire Matériaux et Durabilité des Constructions, LMDC-INSA, Université de Toulouse, UPS, INSA, 135, Avenue de Rangueil, F-31 077 Toulouse, France

of the strong sensitivity of geopolymerization reactions to the temperature. This risks to inhibit the reactions while ignoring the strong thermal potential of this hot region.

In addition, it has been shown that the chemical composition of the precursor, particularly the percentage of reactive calcium compounds (CaO), has a significant impact on the course of the geopolymerization reactions, especially at young age. Thus, slag, class C fly ash, lime, Portland cement, or CCR (calcium carbide residue) which all have in common a high content of CaO ($\geq 30\%$), are often used in substitution (between 5 and 20%) of the precursors containing low CaO ($< 10\%$). This allows to improve the mechanical resistance due to the formation of additional reaction products including CASH and CSH (in the case of Portland cement) and, therefore, offering a more compact, denser, and stronger structure to the final product [3].

Within that family of calcium compounds, the use of CCR can be more beneficial for the environment. Indeed, CCR is an industrial by-product from the manufacture of acetylene. Its high alkalinity is a major problem for the environment as it can easily contaminate groundwater when improperly stored. Many studies have attempted to add value to CCR by using it as an activator or substituent in geopolymers due to its high alkaline, pH above 12. Although these studies are promising, the effect of the curing temperatures has not yet been fully investigated when CCR is used in a geopolymer system [5]. Therefore, the present study aims at assessing the effect of two ambient curing conditions on the physico-mechanical properties of metakaolin-based geopolymer concrete containing calcium carbide residue. Thus, a curing condition commonly encountered in the literature (20 °C) will be compared to a curing condition closer to the climatic context of the study area (30 °C).

Materials and experimental methods

The kaolin clay was collected from the city of Ouagadougou. It was previously dried, crushed, sieved on 80 μm sieve, and then calcined at 700 °C [6] for 3 h, with a heating rate of 10 °C/min, to produce amorphous and reactive metakaolin-based aluminosilicates. The cooling was done slowly until the temperature in the oven reached room temperature (around 30 °C). The CCR was collected from the waste storage site, in Ouagadougou, of a local company as an industrial by-product exposed to the open air. It was sun dried, crushed, and sieved through an 80 μm sieve. It was previously used to improve compressive strength of compressed earth blocks [7].

The values of specific density of MK and CCR are 2.67 and 2.42 g/cm^3 , determined using helium pycnometer. The laser particle size analysis shows that the median particle sizes are 10.93 μm and 12.65 μm , respectively, for MK and

CCR. The specific gravity analysis indicates that the CCR is less dense than the calcined clay. The laser granulometry analysis indicates that both MK and CCR have almost the same fineness. The chemical composition of the materials indicates that the CCR is very rich in CaO ($> 66\%$), while the MK contains only traces of CaO (0.1%). The MK is mainly composed of SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 at a cumulative content of 96.2%. The TGA analysis performed on the raw clay showed the mass loss event at 550 °C, corresponding to the dehydroxylation of the main kaolinite clay mineral.

A river sand and gravel obtained from a local company were used for the production of concrete. The granulometric analysis shows that the sand has a well-distributed particle size with a fineness modulus of 2.28 and HAZEN uniformity coefficient (Cu) of 3.33, which makes it particularly suitable for the production of concrete, while gravel has a uniform particle distribution (Cu = 1.43).

The composition of the geopolymer concrete was designed referring to Cao et al. [8]. The control, noted 0%CCR, is a geopolymer concrete whose precursor is only calcined clay (MK) powder activated with NaOH 12 M [9]; aggregates (sand and gravel). Then, a part of the MK is substituted by CCR at content of 10% and 15% (Table 1). The optimal substitution of calcium-rich material in geopolymer systems is known to be around 15%. Further calcium addition tends to weaken its mechanical strength [10]. The first step of the preparation of concrete consists of mixing the aggregates (gravel + sand) and the precursor (MK + CCR). After homogenization of the mixtures, the NaOH solution is added gradually while mixing in the electric mixer. The mixing time is 5 min (05).

The setting time was measured on the geopolymer paste with VICAT apparatus at 20 °C and 30 °C. The consistency of the concrete was determined by measuring the slump using Abram's mini-cone in accordance with the NF EN 12,350-2 [11]. The demolding of the concrete was done 24 h after the end of the setting. The concrete was cured, covered with plastic to limit moisture loss until the desired date, at two different temperatures (20 °C and 30 °C), which represent respectively the minimum and the average ambient temperature in the study region (Ouagadougou). The measured relative humidity under the plastic cover is around $50 \pm 10\%$

Table 1 Mix design of the concrete

Material (kg/m^3)	0%CCR	10%CCR	15%CCR
MK	350	315	298
CCR	0	35	53
NaOH pellets	126	126	126
Water	229	229	229
Sand	723	723	723
Gravel	958	958	958

Fig. 1 Setting times of geopolymer pastes

during the curing period. Compressive strength tests are performed on $\varnothing 50\text{mm} \times \text{H}100\text{mm}$ cylindrical specimens in accordance with NF EN 12,390-3 [12].

Results and discussion

The setting time of geopolymer paste

Figure 1 shows that the initial and final setting times for the reference paste are 545 min and 745 min, respectively, at 20 °C; 390 and 750 min at 30 °C. For this paste, the temperature has no much effect on the setting. When metakaolin is replaced by CCR, the setting times increase for both temperatures. At 20 °C, the substitution of MK with 10% CCR increased the initial setting time of 7.2 times (390 to 3200 min). The same observation is made for the final setting time, which increased 4.9 times (750 to 4450 min). At 30 °C, the substitution of MK with 10% CCR increased the initial setting time 1.3 times (545 to 1265 min). The same observation is made for the final setting time, which increased 1.4 times (750 to 1790 min). Therefore, there is 1.5 times decrease on both setting times by increasing the temperature from 20 to 30 °C for geopolymer containing 10% CCR. Similar evolution was recorded after substitution with 15% CCR.

Many phenomena are involved in the setting of geopolymers. Calcium products likely to cause exothermic reactions such as portland cements accelerate the setting of geopolymeric pastes by the contribution of the excessive heat released during the reaction [8]. The CCR, being very rich in CaO, the delay in its setting is in contradiction with these observations of the literature. Moreover, the results indicate that when CCR is introduced in the geopolymer paste, the setting time is strongly affected compared to the control paste containing 100%MK. These observations could be related to the high alkalinity of CCR [13]. Indeed, it has

been shown that although a highly alkaline medium is necessary for the proper progress of geopolymerization, an excessive alkaline medium tends to inhibit it [14]. The additional delay of the setting observed when the temperature goes from 30 to 20 °C would be only an amplification of this phenomenon already generated by the additional alkalinity brought by the addition of the CCR.

Workability

The addition of CCR decreases the workability of geopolymer concrete. The parameters that affect the workability are essentially the specific surface areas of the materials, which are related to the shape and fineness of their constituent particles. The higher water demand of CCR compared to MK could be related to the specific surface area. In addition, the difference in specific gravity between MK and CCR could also be the reason for the observed decrease in workability. Indeed, the concrete mix design method adopted consists in a mass substitution. The densities determined by helium pycnometer showed that CCR is 10.33% less dense than MK. Thus, for 15% substitution of MK by CCR, the contribution of CCR would represent an extra 10.3% of MK equivalent volume in the reference concrete for the same amount of NaOH solution. This could be one of the reasons why a decrease in workability is observed when MK is substituted by CCR. In most cases, the workability of concrete is reduced when a CaO-rich compound is introduced into it. Askarian et al. have observed that the introduction of Portland cement in geopolymer concrete has reduced its workability [3].

Apparent density

Figure 2 shows that the density of the concretes under both curing conditions is approximately 2200 kg/m³ for all of the mix designs. It can be seen that all the samples lose a small part of their mass (water loss) between the 7th and 28th day,

Fig. 2 Bulk density of geopolymer concrete

regardless of the storage conditions. These results would indicate that the concretes stored at 30 °C did not suffer from more water loss compared to those stored at 20 °C. Previous studies made by [2, 15] show similar density for geopolymer concretes (2200–2300 kg/m³).

Compressive strength

Figure 3 presents the results of the compressive strength. At 7 days, the reference concrete has a strength of 6.1 and 10.8 MPa, respectively, at 20 and 30 °C. Although the setting times are similar, an increase of 10 °C results in a strength gain of +76%. Between 7 and 14 days, the gain in strength of the reference concrete is around 48% and 38% for concretes stored at 20° and 30 °C, respectively. It shows that the concrete stored at 30 °C seems to reach its targeted compressive strength faster than the one at 20 °C. This confirms the observations made by previous studies showing that heating geopolymer concretes tend to accelerate geopolymerization reaction [2],

Moreover, the substitution of MK with CCR led to a decrease in the strength of the geopolymer concrete for both curing temperatures, at 7 days. This decrease in strength is related to the increase in setting time caused by CCR: a longer setting time leads to a lower strength development at younger age. This observation is confirmed by the higher 7-day strengths of the samples stored at 30 °C compared to those stored at 20 °C. At 7 days, the concrete containing 10%CCR has a resistance 72% higher at 30° than its value at 20 °C, i.e., an increase from 3.1 to 5.3 MPa. At 14 days, the concrete containing 15%CCR shows a greater improvement in compressive strength than the concrete containing 10%CCR. Between day 7 and day 14, its strength increases from 3.1 to 12 MPa (+287%) and from 5.2 to 15.2 MPa (+192%) when stored at 20 and 30 °C, respectively. Although the 7-day strengths are lower compared to the reference concrete, all the samples containing CCR tend to outperform the reference concrete

Fig. 3 Compressive strength of geopolymer concretes

at day 14. Similar observation was made at 28 days where all samples containing CCR showed higher compressive strength than the reference concrete regardless of curing conditions. From this observation, it can be concluded that the industrial by-product CCR tends to improve the mechanical performance of geopolymer concrete. Nevertheless, long-term results (90 days) are necessary to confirm this statement.

Conclusion

The objective of this study was to assess the effect of the curing temperature on the physical and mechanical properties of metakaolin-based geopolymer concretes containing CCR. The results indicate that the substitution of MK with CCR and curing temperature has various effects on the concretes:

- ✓ The CCR increases the setting time of the paste and decreases the workability of concrete.
- ✓ The concretes have longer setting time when they are cured at 20 °C than 30 °C.
- ✓ The mechanical strength at early age is affected by the addition of CCR as well as the curing temperature: CCR tends to lower the strength at 7 days. At day 14, CCR improves the mechanical strength of the reference concrete.
- ✓ The compressive strength is improved by about 60% for the control concrete and by 25% for the concrete containing 15% CCR at 14 days, when the curing temperature is increased from 20 to 30 °C.

The curing temperature of 30 °C (laboratory room temperature of the study area) and the substitution of MK by CCR improve the mechanical strength of geopolymer concretes at early age. Nevertheless, the behavior at long-term and microstructural analyses are necessary for a better understanding of the performance of geopolymer concrete cured at room temperature.

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Declarations

Conflict of interest There are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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